

Analysis of the Development Strategies of Cultural and Creative Industry in Small Towns of Western Zhejiang

Dandong Ge, and Lei Tong

Abstract—This paper studies the cultural creative industry's characteristics between the eastern and western of Zhejiang Province. Through the Comparative analysis, this paper works out that the cultural creative industry in western Zhejiang Province is mainly promoted by the inside force, and its level of development is obviously much lower than the eastern Zhejiang Province whose cultural creative industry is mainly pulled by outside forces. So this paper worked out some strategies for the development of cultural creative industry in western Zhejiang Province, which are based on the economic foundation and the cultural resource endowments. Finally these strategies will help to improve the whole development level of western Zhejiang Province, and contribute to the balance development between the west and east of Zhejiang Province.

Keywords—Cultural creative industry; underdeveloped; western Zhejiang; strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the context of social and economic restructuring, cultural creative industry has become an important choice for such a restructuring. Though the cultural and creative industry is a new industry and its history is short, it actually shows great potential. So it is very necessary to do some research on cultural and creative industry especially in China which is developing rapidly. So this paper chose Changshan a small town in western Zhejiang province whose economic development is in a low level compared with other towns in Zhejiang as a case to study what strategies it can take to develop its cultural and creative industry.

II. OVERVIEW OF CULTURAL AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT

A. Concept and Connotation of Cultural and Creative Industries

Currently, there is no unified definition on the concept of cultural and creative industries. Different countries have different definitions. For example, "the special working group of creative industries" in England (1998) and the "Economic Affairs Industrial Development Bureau" (2007) in Taiwan China, both believe that something as long as the talent,

Dandong Ge is an associate professor of Department of Regional & Urban Planning Department, College of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, China.(Phone: +8613957109333; e-mail: zjugdd@126.com)

Lei Tong is with the Regional & Urban Planning Department, College of Civil Engineering and Architecture, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou, China. (e-mail: tonglei_517@yahoo.cn).

wisdom, creative and culture can provide jobs and create wealth through a certain way(industrial development), and then it can be called creative industries(cultural and creative industries)[1]-[2]. While Chinese scholar, Jin Yuanpu emphasized that the cultural and creative industries is a new industry which is based on high-tech, relying on the latest mode of transmission (network)[3].

Based on the socio-economic, scientific, and technological development level of small towns in western Zhejiang, this paper argues that the cultural and creative industries should not be high-tech threshold limit, as long as something that is related to culture and creative and it can be produced Industrialization, large-scale and create wealth then it can be called cultural and creative industries. This paper argues that the cultural and creative industries should contain two levels connotation. One is using creation to make culture industrial production, and another is through adding culture and creative elements into the existing industry, to improve the production.

B. Status and Prospects of Cultural and Creative Industries

1. Cultural and Creative Industries Started Late, Developing Rapidly and is becoming to be the 21st Century Sunrise Industry

As a national industrial policy, the concept of Cultural and creative industries was first put forward by the special working group of creative industries which was established in 1997. Subsequently, the United States, South Korea, Japan launched their own cultural industry policies. And in 2000 China, first officially presented its cultural policies in China's tenth National Economic and Social Development Planning.

Fig. 1 Added value and growth rate of China's cultural and creative industry from 2005-2010

Since 2000, China's cultural and creative industry has achieved rapid development. In 2005, China's cultural and creative industrial added value reached 421.6 billion Yuan.

And in 2010 the cultural and creative industrial added value exceeded 1.1 trillion Yuan (figure 1). From 2005 to 2010 the cultural and creative industrial added value had reached an average annual growth rate of 17%, which was significantly higher than the growth rate of the GDP and other new emerging industries. Thus the cultural and creative industry has also become the 21st century sunrise industry in China. And due to the vigorous development of cultural and creative industries, the year 2009 was named "the first year of the cultural and creative" in China.

2.The Development Pace of Cultural and Creative Industries will Further Accelerate and become a Pillar Industry of Many Cities

In China the active policy conditions will further promote the development of cultural and creative industries. Such as, in 2009, the State Council promulgated the "Cultural Industry Promotion Plan" in which it enhance the development of cultural industries to the height of a national strategy. In 2010 in the file "the CPC Central Committee's proposal on the Formulating the 12th Five-Year Plan for National Economic and Social Development" first proposed "to promote the cultural industry become a pillar industry of the national economy ". March 2011, the government work report of the State Council clearly pointed out that "we should vigorously develop the cultural industry, cultivate a new type of culture industry, and promote the cultural industry to become a pillar industry of the national economy". All these policies mean that in the "12th Five-Year period, the cultural industry will play an increasingly important role in the transformation of economic development mode and the adjusting of industrial structure. And development the cultural and creative industries will no doubt be an important choice for China's economic restructuring.

Data show that in 2010, the cultural and creative industries added value in Beijing was 169.22 billion Yuan, which accounting for 12.3% of the city's GDP; In Shanghai the cultural and creative industries added value was about 163 billion Yuan, accounting for 9.6% of the city's GDP; in Guangdong the increased value of cultural industries was 252.4 billion Yuan, accounting for 5.6% of the province's GDP; in Yunnan its increased value of cultural industries was 440 billion Yuan, accounting for 6.1 percent of the city's GDP. Thus the cultural industry has become a strategic pillar industry of these cities actually. In accordance to the international standards, as long as the added value of cultural industries shares more than 5% of the GDP, then it can be called pillar industry¹.

III. FEATURE ANALYSIS OF CULTURAL AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT IN ZHEJIANG

A. The Development of Cultural and Creative Industries in Zhejiang is in the Forefront of China, but the Development in Western and Eastern is Unbalanced

The report of "the cultural industry development index of

Chinese provinces and cities" which was given by the Renmin University of China, released that the cultural industry development index of Zhejiang ranked fourth, just after the Beijing, Shanghai and Guangdong, which showed that The development of cultural and creative industries in Zhejiang is in the forefront of China. While, in Zhejiang, the development of cultural and creative industries are unbalance in its western and eastern. More than 50% of the province's cultural and creative industry was concentrated in the eastern coastal town of Zhejiang and Hangzhou acted as a leader. As of 2009, there were 31 cultural and creative industrial parks, whose construction area were over 30000 square meters and their annual revenues were over 300 million yuan. During these 31 parks, 21 of them were located in Hangzhou, Ningbo, Zhoushan, and only 7 were located in the West Region, such as Quzhou, Lishui. What is more the Cultural and creative industries development plan (2009-2015) of Zhejiang Province put forward 10 Cultural and creative industries concentrated area, 90% of these concentrated area were Located in Eastern Zhejiang coastal areas; 10% Distributed in middle region of Zhejiang(Jinhua), and 0% located in western Zhejiang province(Quzhou, Lishui)[4].

Fig. 2 The zoning of Zhejiang

TABLE II
THE COMPARISON OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT BETWEEN WESTERN ZHEJIANG AND EASTERN ZHEJIANG

	Changshan	Anji
the reception of domestic and foreign Tourists (million)	17.5	774
total foreign trade volume (million U.S. dollars)	13050	193788
Foreign-funded enterprise	3	22
The contract use of foreign capital (million U.S. dollars)	25100	1478

¹ in accordance to the international standards, as long as the added value of cultural industries share more than 5% of the GDP, then it can be called pillar industry.

TABLE I
 THE COMPARISON OF CULTURAL CREATIVE INDUSTRIES DEVELOPMENT IN DIFFERENT PARTS OF ZHEJIANG PROVINCE

	Eastern Zhejiang	Middle region of Zhejiang	Western Zhejiang
The capacity of introduce foreign investment	strength	moderate	weak
Export capacity	strength	strength	weak
economic develope basis	strength	moderate	weak
uman resources support conditions	strength	ordinary	weak
innovative development capability	strength	ordinary	weak
Technology Development level	strength	ordinary	weak
Government-led force	strength	strength	ordinary
Typical representative	Hangzhou(animation)	Yiwu(Small Commodities)	Quzhou(Confucius Culture)
The dominant Type of culture and creative industries	Animation games, industrial design, software development, advertising design, architectural design, film and television culture	Arts and Crafts design, manufacturing design, fashion design	Outstanding historical, cultural research and display; local characteristics culture show

A. Two Different Characteristics of the Development Mode (Eastern Zhejiang: External Pull + Western Zhejiang: Internal Forces Push)

On the development of cultural and creative industries, there are significant differences among the eastern, western and middle areas of Zhejiang province. The development of its cultural and creative industries of the towns in eastern Zhejiang, mainly rely on its predominant geographical location, and largely dependent on the introduction of Capital, technology, talent and the output of its products. What is more, the governments of these towns play an dominant role in the development of the cultural and creative industries, and its development mode is a typical external pull mode. In contrast, the development of cultural and creative industries in western Zhejiang are much weaker than eastern Zhejiang, and its town governments also plays an weaker role in the construction of cultural and creative industries and its development mode is a typical internal forces push mode. Table I, II compares the developments of cultural and creative industries in eastern, western and middle areas of Zhejiang, which offers a further evidence to prove that the development modes of cultural and creative industries in eastern Zhejiang and Western Zhejiang are different.

IV. DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY FOR THE SMALL TOWNS' CULTURAL AND CREATIVE INDUSTRIES IN WESTERN ZHEJIANG

A. Planning in Advance, Joint Development of the Urban and Rural Areas

Cultural and creative industries as an industry is an important part of urban construction and in terms of social life or social production, cultural and creative industries involve a lot of complicated details. Therefore, the development of cultural and creative industries should be planed ahead, through scientific research on status quo and condition, making a reasonable plan to provide guidance and management basis for the development of cultural and creative industries. In addition, during the relevant planning studies, it is necessary to give overall consideration on the urban and rural areas, in order to achieve the joint development.

On one hand, urban and rural co-ordinate development is the trend of urban development and also national policy requirements. On the other hand, the historical and cultural heritages, especially traditional folk lifestyle, as well as the ecological landscape resources, are mostly concentrated in the countryside.

B. Integrate Resources, Making the Industry Cross and Collaborative Development

Historical and cultural resources with a wide range, small-scale, decentralization, as well as the lack in characteristics are the important features of western Zhejiang small town cultural resources. The so-called resource integration contains two aspects; one is the interpretation, selection and classification in all kinds of original resources of the historical culture and natural landscape. The second is to combine the resources through industrialization organic space or tourism industry.

Industry cross and collaborative development refers to intersecting in cultural resources and the existing manufacturing, tourism and other industries. Through the industrialization of cultural resources and existing industrial (industry) to transform and upgrade the two ways and means to realize the coordinated development between different industries, and ultimately promote the development and upgrading of the urban economy[5].

C. Strengthen Regional Cooperation to Jointly Focus on Fostering a Characteristic Industry

Small towns in western Zhejiang, the cultural resources monomer, existing industry resources monomer, or various small towns, their competitiveness are at a low level. Therefore, we should strengthen mutual cooperation between the small towns, forma the western Zhejiang small towns Union, nurture and build together with the regional characteristics of a specialized industry, to promote the region as a whole the rise and development of cultural and creative industries. Such as the small towns in western Zhejiang, they generally have good ecological and cultural resources, historical and cultural resources, and rely on high-speed rail and highway traffic, locate in the traffic circle in Hangzhou, Shanghai within 2 to 3 hours. They can develop tourism industry, and make tourism as the main line to lead the development of cultural and creative industries.

Fig. 3 The comparison of the per capita GDP between Changshan and other towns in Zhejiang Province

D. Make the Small Towns be Distinctive Characteristic Towns and Allow Different Elements Co-Exist in the Towns

The small towns in western Zhejiang developing cultural and creative industries should base on its rich tradition history and cultural resources, as well as ecological and cultural resources to build a special culture brand belonging to the western Zhejiang.

The same time, we should pay attention to the frontier city of Hangzhou, Shanghai to keep up with the trends of the international community and introduce advanced ideas, science and technology to form a wide range of cultural and creative industries system.

It not only guarantees the protection of historical and cultural resources and heritage, but also realizes the integration with the social forefront and social development trend.

V. CASE STUDY

A. Model Introduction

The Model is a small town (hereinafter referred to as the Changshan County) in less developed areas. Its economic development characteristics, historical and cultural development features have strong similarities with western other small towns in Zhejiang. It's strong typical and representative model in western Zhejiang.

1. The Geographic Conditions

The Changshan county has a favorable geographical condition, located in the throat of Fujian, Zhejiang, Jiangxi and Anhui provinces, known as the "first stop Liangzhe, eight provinces thorough Quzhou,". 320 State Road, 205 National Highway and Hangzhou-Jinhua-Quzhou Highway Huang Qu South Expressway intersect in the territory.

It's 40 kilometers from the Zhejiang-Jiangxi railway and Quzhou Airport Railway.

2. The Development of the History

Changshan County has a long history, dating back five or six thousand years ago. In the long development process it steeped in a rich historical and cultural heritage.

3. The Development of Socio-Economic Status Quo

Changshan County's level of socio-economic development is in the low level, the overall economic strength and technological development are not strong (Figure 3). In 2011 the GDP of Changshan County is 88.6 million, per capita GDP was 26,610 yuan (equivalent to \$ 4 120), far below of Zhejiang Province of per capita GDP58665 yuan (equivalent to \$ 9,083).

B. Present Development Situation of Cultural and Creative Industry in Changshan Town

1. The development Level of Cultural and Creative Industries in Changshan is Low

The develop level of cultural and creative industries in Changshan is low, it is almost at the initial stage, and it has not formed a system yet. The inputs and outputs of Changshan's cultural and creative industry are at a low level. 2010, the per people's cultural capital was 51.27 yuan, which is lower than Zhejiang province's level. What is more, the added value of cultural industry in Changshan accounted for 0.66% of the whole town's GDP. This data was also lower than Zhejiang province's and China's, whose level is 3.8% and 2.74%.

2. The Cultural and Creative Industry are Scattered Distribution and Lack of Integration

Changshan town still does not have a clear coordinate system for which can be taken reference by Changshan's definition and classification of cultural and creative industries. And the statistical standards are not uniform. Due to such facts, it is always difficult to distinguish "cultural industry" and "cultural and creative industry ". In addition, the cultural and creative industries now distribute in various industries and lack integration. At present, there is no industrial park in Changshan town, which is related to cultural and creative industries. Neither do such facts be beneficial to dig out the potential benefits of cultural and creative industries, nor do it be good for the management of the relevant departments.

3. The Development of the Sources is in a Low-End Level and the Added Value is also in Low Level

Most of the development and utilization of historical culture resources, natural resources and landscape resources is still

stay in primary processing and development stage. The added values of outputs also stay in a low level, and the input and output ratio is also low. For example, Changshan has rich resources of ornamental stones, but the ornamental stone resources is mainly produced, transported and sold by single family. Such Sporadic, scattered, individuals, spontaneous acts of purchase and sale, seriously hampers the large-scale development of the market, which also adds difficult to foster large-scale, intensive management enterprises and personalized products. Moreover, during the stone processing, due to the limited capacity of producing and processing, most of the produce process is stay in the primary processing of raw materials stage. Actually, its essence is a behavior of sale raw materials unidirectionally, which on the one hand leads to products with low added value, and on the other hand, in the long run, it is an unsustainable model of development.

C. Ways and Means of the Development of Cultural and Creative Industries in Case City

1. Cultural Strategy

Cognize and remodel the cultural image, and make the industrial development direction consistent with the cultural connotation of Changshan County.

Reread and reclassify the various kinds of cultural resources of Changshan County, then make analysis and evaluation about them from different perspectives such as the characteristics or regional competitiveness of the resource with the help of questionnaire survey and map contact method, and eventually sort out five kinds of cultural themes (thoroughfare culture, geological culture, Huyou culture, stone culture, nonmaterial culture heritages culture) which can reflect the native temperament of Changshan County as the five directions of cultural and creative industries development which can serve as the guidance and control for the industry type that need to be focus on.

2. Industry Strategy

Innovate the optimization approach of cultural resource, focus on fostering and mining cultural and creative industries carrier that has geographical characteristics.

Combine the cultural resources with existing traditional industries of Changshan County by making use of the strong industry relevance of the cultural creative industries, for instance, combine the nonmaterial culture heritages with tourism industry, innovate the optimization approach of nonmaterial culture heritages industry, and aggressively build new carriers for cultural creative industries. The plan studied and determined five perspectives of industrial development strategies and approaches, and the key cultural creative industries which need to be constructed and developed recently, as shown in Table III.

D. Spatial Strategies

Construct the cultural creative industrial spatial pattern that can adapt to the city culture. The development of the cultural creative industries should adhere to the co-ordination of culture, industry, space.

The most direct effect way is to industrialize the culture industry and creative industry, and carry it out in space, providing support for the development of cultural and creative industries. After planning and survey, the Changshan County determine the cultural creative industries space layout structure of "one core, two corridors, three groups", integrating the cultural and creative industries by spatial agglomeration, as shown in Figure 4. On one hand, integrate the culture and industries through space, on the other hand, spatial agglomeration is conducive to generate economies of scale, and also is ease of operation and management.

Fig. 4 Spatial layout of cultural creative industries in ChangShan town

VI. CONCLUSION

Zhejiang Province is a big province, and there is difference between the eastern area and the western area when it comes to cultural creative industries development. In one way, ZHEJIANG Province can be regarded as a microcosm of China, so the study of developing the cultural creative industries is quite important for Zhejiang Province, especially for cities and towns in the western Zhejiang. When constructing cultural creative industries, they should stimulate actively the inner power, base on the characteristics of the local culture, depend on its good ecological landscape resources and historical and cultural resources, promote the economic transformation and development of the western region of Zhejiang Province and actively pursue the eastern area with the help of cultural creative industries by mainly developing traditional formats such as folk performance, folk craft and folk tourism, relying on the convenient transportation brought by the China's high iron strategy, firmly grasping the pulse of The Times, in order to narrow the gap and realize the balanced development between the eastern and western Zhejiang.

TABLE III
 THE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES OF CULTURAL CREATIVE INDUSTRIES IN CHANGSHAN TOWN

	Industrialization path	Key projects in recent
Thoroughfare cultural	Commerce distribution industry(Logistics industry) Transportation industry Travel distribution industry	Business, commerce and cultural center in western Zhejiang; Tourism hub; Logistics center;
Geological cultural	develope science exhibition; develope expedition tourism;	Changshan geological museum; Theme cultural monuments;
Stone cultural	ornamental stones large-scale develope; Add art to the stone processing; Develope high-end stone processing industry	The ornamental stones cultural creative garden; Strange stone market; Features Stone Exposition;
Huyou origin cultural	Add creative ideas to enhance the added value of Huyou; Combine with tourism, develope Huyou cultural actives, for example the Huyou harvest festival;	Huyou culture Creative Park; Huyou Culture Exposition; leisure agriculture park of Huyou theme;
Intangible cultural heritage	Integration of cultural resources, and make them to be important resource of tourism; In combination with other industries, to make different use of intangible cultural heritage;	Intangible Cultural Heritage Creative Industry Park; Changshan folk snacks street; Changshan ancient architecture Exposition

REFERENCES

- [1] Huang Zhifeng. Literature review on creative industry [J]. Chongqing Social Sciences, 2010(5):69-71.
- [2] Jin Yuanpu. The global prosperity of creative industry [J]. Social Outlook, 2005(2):22-24.
- [3] Jin Yuanpu. Cultural creative industries:the strategic choice of innovative China[N]. People's Daily, 2006-12-29(14).
- [4] The Development Plan of Cultural Creative Industries of Zhejiang Province [Z].Reform and Development Plan of Zhejiang Province, 2009,12.
- [5] CCID Consulting. Research on cultural integration of assets path[R].Beijing: City Economic Research Center, 2010(1):31-34.